

Proposed Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) to Increase Patient Visits of Assyifa Specialist Clinic

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ABSTRACT: The Covid-19 pandemic has caused a catastrophe in the healthcare sector and a customer shifting trend in how patients choosing a healthcare service as their medication platform. Furthermore, social media and internet users are both rapidly rising and individuals nowadays are also prone to being more aware of their health concerns. Healthcare services that are incapable to compete within the industry, survive the business and adapt to the changing consumer behavior will likely face the major issues. This study analyzed the business problem of Assyifa Specialist Clinic who faced a decreased in the patient visits and revenue in surviving the private clinic in the midst of Covid-19 outbreak. The author used Segmenting, Targeting and Positioning (STP), Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) and value proposition canvas analysis through the quantitative research method to propose the marketing strategy to increase patient visit of Assyifa Specialist Clinic. The study found that there is still lack of clinic promotion and the access of clinic information is still low. Meanwhile, the current customers of Assyifa Specialist Clinic are mostly critical, curious, high self-awareness, smart and oversharing behaviors with health conscious, social media users, technology savvy, financially literate, well-educated and hygiene conscious lifestyle and in middle to high income level. To overcome, the gap between the Assyifa Specialist Clinic and the customers, the author intends to propose new marketing strategy as the business solution of Assyifa Specialist Clinic issue.

KEYWORDS: Customer shifting; Healthcare service; Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC); Segmenting; Targeting and Positioning (STP); Value proposition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Covid-19 pandemic has brought a huge chaotic to the healthcare industry in Indonesia. There was a dramatic increase of medical service demands, because Covid-19 virus has escalated a new yet complex medical services, screening and testing suspected cases contact tracing, isolation of cases and managing severe cases [4]. Thus, it required the expanding of new services, the improvement of healthcare capacity, the resilience of human resources and high expenditure of operational cost. For those healthcare services who are incapable of providing comprehensive Covid-19 services, compete within the industry and survive the business will probably face a continuous crisis. The Indonesian Private Hospital Association (ARSSI) stated that the Covid-19 pandemic had affected the operations of several hospitals in Indonesia. Even the cash flow of the hospital was also disrupted due to the drastic decline in the number of visits from non-Covid-19 patients. During the pandemic, private hospitals, especially in the red zone, the decrease in outpatient care is about 50 to 60 percent, meanwhile for inpatient treatment, a drop in patient volume was ranged from 40 to 60 percent, this phenomena has an impact on cash flow at the hospital [5]. The same thing also happened to most clinics in Indonesia. The decrease in cash flow at the clinic will have a major impact on the clinic's operations. During this pandemic, operational costs have also increased significantly due to the enormous needs to deal with this pandemic. If this happens along with a decrease in the volume of patient visits, this will also endanger the sustainability of a clinic [3]. Therefore, several steps must be taken in order to maintain clinic operation, increase patient visits volume and recover the clinic's revenue in this e Covid-19 pandemic era.

Assyifa Specialist Clinic (the real name is disguised for company confidentiality concern) is a private clinic that established since 1987 in South Jakarta, Indonesia. It provides general and specialist care including general consultation and emergency care, specialist care that consist of pediatric, ENT, dermatology and venereology, neurology, dental and psychologist. Besides, Assyifa Specialist Clinic also collaborated with the famous physiotherapy institution to offer physiotherapy services such as pediatric physiotherapy, stroke service and general physiotherapy. Assyifa Specialist Clinic also provides medical supporting facilities such

as laboratory, EEG (Electroencephalography) testing and ambulance as well as pharmacy. Before Covid-19 pandemic occurred, Assyifa's operation was doing fine and all business activities and services were conducted by face-to-face visits and treatment. There wasn't any significant drop in the number of patient visits until Covid-19 positive cases arose in April 2020. Total number of patient visits in the year 2019 was at 14.180 visitors, it kept declining as of September 2022, the total number of patient visits was only at 6.135. Assuming the clinic can obtain 9.000 visitors at the end of year 2022, still the average CAGR of 2019 to 2022 resulted at -11. As yet, the number of patient visits hasn't returned to the same amount as before Covid-19 happened, even though the total number of visitors in the year 2022 has started to peak up. The decrease in patient visits has influenced the decrease in revenue as well with average CAGR of -18% from year 2019 to 2021.

The decrease in number of patient visits happened, because Assyifa had to maintain the safety of health workers and patients as well as the quality of the service, so Assyifa took a brave decision to conduct all of the remaining specialist practice including pediatrics, ENT, dermatology and venereology, neurology and psychologist by online through telemedicine, the operational hours of emergency care and general consultation from 24 hours were shortened to 8 am until 10 pm and closed the dental practice and rontgen service for temporary. The rest services that operated were emergency care, general consultation, laboratory and physiotherapy. Moreover, in the midst of a decrease in the number of patient visits which also led to a decrease in revenue, the operational costs for running services in the Covid-19 pandemic was rising. Therefore, to strengthen the resurgence of the clinic, so that the volume of visitors in the following years can return/ increase from the amount of visitors in year 2019 (before Covid-19) in a short period of time, Assyifa has to develop new strategies to prevent loss further by increasing the volume of patient visits. This study aims to determinine the relevant Segmentation, Targeting and Positioning (STP) and develop a new Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) and value proposition strategy of Assyifa Specialist Clinic, since Assyifa has never been changed and adapted to the new strategy with current changes in the environment and customer shifting trend.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Segmentation, Targeting and Positioning (STP)

Target market is divided into 3 steps which are market segmentation, market targeting and market positioning. Market segmentation contains a group of customers who share the same interests, needs and wants. The variables involve geographic, demographic, psychographic and behavioral aspects as well as operating variables, purchasing decisions and situational factors. Meanwhile, market targeting can be done by divided into 4 criterias including mass market, multiple segments, single/ niche markets and individuals. Once the company has already established its customer's target market and the nature of the competitions, then the company can determine the suitable points-of-difference and points- of-parity brand associations. Points of Difference (PODs) describes the values perceived by having a strong connection of a brand, accurately evaluating and the differentiation aspect that isn't available on any other competitor's brand offered. While, the points- of-parity means the value associated by having unnecessary differentiation/ unique aspects but it is shared with the existing brand [2].

2.2 Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC)

Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC) is defined as a comprehensive planning process of designing the suitable marketing communications to ensure the customers gain a strong connection through the message delivered of a product or service offered in a relevant and sustainable manner [2]. IMC tries to assess, combine and integrate numerous communication approaches to give a clear, consistent, and the most possible impact. Besides, IMC also helps companies to develop a marketing communication strategy effectively and efficiently which involving coverage, contribution, commonality, complementarity, conformability and cost. The marketing communication platforms consist of advertising, sales promotion, events and experience, public relations and publicity, online and social media marketing, mobile marketing, direct and database marketing and personal selling. Each platform has its own purposes, characteristics and cost that has to be adjusted with the company's requirements. There are several steps in establishing the marketing communication strategy as follows (1) determine the target market, (2) assign the communications purposes, (3) create the communications, (4) choose the communications channels, (5) arrange the communications budget required, (6) decide the communications mix, (7) evaluate the communications results, and (8) manage the integrated marketing communications process.

2.3 Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC)

The value proposition encompasses the entire set of advantages that the business guarantees that the customers will receive proposition through a set of benefits of the company's product or service offers. The company's offering, which can be a combination of goods, services, knowledge, information and experiences, transforms the intangible value proposition into something tangible. The value proposition canvas consist of [1].

1. Gain creators: describe how a product or service offered can provide the benefits, solution and value added to the customers.
2. Pain relievers: describe how a product or service offered can eliminate the customer's pains and problems.
3. Product and service: the product and service offered which provides gain and pain relieve can help customers accomplish the functional, interpersonal and emotional goals.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research will conduct a quantitative descriptive method through the distribution of online questionnaires which aims to determine and evaluate the current STP of the Assyifa Specialist Clinic, the suitable Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) and the value proposition approaches to increase the numbers of patient visits in Assyifa Specialist Clinic. The researcher gathered the primary and secondary data which the primary data of this research will be collected through observation and questionnaire. The questionnaires will be formed and distributed online to the patient and/or the family of patients who have visited and received the medical treatment from Assyifa Specialist Clinic. The author determines the sample size of this study is 100, as this amount is the minimum sample size of quantitative research. Meanwhile, the secondary data of this research uses the company's data and literature from company profile, search engine, journals, previous theses and E-books in order to increase understanding and achieve reliable information and data regarding the healthcare industry. Next, the result of this research will be analysed and formulated through STP, Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) and value proposition framework.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Segmentation, Targeting and Positioning (STP)

In this STP analysis, the author used demographic and geographic variable that consist of age, gender, domicile, occupation, education and monthly expense. Then, psychographic and behavioral variable including the frequency of visiting the clinic, the reason, main motivation, the major influence, preferred type of service, average monthly expenditure, preferred payment method, preferred medication method, customer touchpoints, preferred communication channels and preferred social media to get information regarding the clinic. Next, purchasing decision variables contains of access and location; the aesthetic appeal, comfort and safety of the clinic environment; promotional; the tariff of medication and treatment; family or relative reviews; income, personal experience, the core and supporting facilities; the doctors and other medical staff quality of service; the service and administration quality and positive reviews from patient/family factor influence customer decision to visit the clinic.

From 110 respondents that the author successfully obtained from Assyifa's customers, the majority of respondents are summarized through STP framework as below:

Table 1. Proposed Market Segmentation

<i>Segmentation</i>	<i>Assyifa Specialist Clinic</i>
Demographic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age: 18 - 55 years old • Sex: Female, male • Occupation: Employee, housewife, student and entrepreneur. • Latest education: Bachelor, master, diploma and highschool. • Monthly Expense: Rp 1.000.0000 – 9.000.000 and > 9.000.000 • Income level: lower-middle to high income level
Geographic	South Tangerang, South Jakarta, Tangerang, Depok and East Jakarta

Psychographic and behavioral	People who visit Assyifa Specialist Clinic 1 – 3x in a year People who seek for medication, accompany sick family member/ relatives and buy medicines People who have self-awareness, the influence from family member/ relatives and doctors People who seek for specialist care, telemedicine, general care and pharmacy People who have average monthly expense to medication Rp 100.000 – Rp 1.000.000 People who pay the medication through self-payment People who seek face to face consultation and telemedicine People who receive the positive review from family/relatives, frequently see or pass by the clinic and influenced by social media People who use search engine and social media such as Instagram, WhatsApp, Youtube and non-social media as well
Purchasing decision	People who seek value from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The doctors and other medical staffs quality of service - Personal experience - Positive reviews from patient/ family of patient - The service and administration quality - The core and supporting facilities - Access and location - The aesthetic appeal, comfort and safety of the clinic environment - The tariff of treatment

After, allocate the segmentation mapping, the newly mapped target market of Assyifa Specialist Clinic will be illustrated as follows:

Table 2. Proposed Target Market

Targeting	Assyifa Specialist Clinic
Geographic	Jabodetabek (Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, Bekasi) area
Gender	Female and male
Age	26 – 55 years old
Occupation	Employee and housewife
Income level	Middle to high income level
Personality	Critical, curious, high self-awareness, smart and generous
Lifestyle	Health conscious, social media users, technology savvy, financially literate, well-educated and hygiene conscious
Benefit Sought	High quality of service, pleasant experience, adequate facilities, positive review, affordable tariff of treatment, strategic location, easy to find, safe and hygienic environment.

The positioning of Assyifa Specialist Clinic should be “a specialist clinic that provides fast and excellent service with qualified and stand-by doctors, affordable price and strategic locations as the solutions to people who seek emergency and limited waiting time.”

4.2 Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC)

4.2.1 Identifying Target Audiences

According to the target market, the target audiences for Assyifa Specialist Clinic is female and male who are 26 – 55 years old and live around Jabodetabek area. Their occupation are employee and housewife with middle to high income level who have health

conscious, social media users, technology savvy, financially literate, well-educated and hygiene conscious as their lifestyle and driven by high quality of service, pleasant experience, adequate facilities, positive review, affordable tariff of treatment, strategic location, easy to find, safe and hygienic environment in determining the place to receive the medication or medical treatment.

4.2.2 Setting the Communications Objectives

Assyifa is famous by its quality of doctors especially its specialist doctors. Assyifa’s specialist doctors are from reputable universities and also practice at leading hospitals in Jakarta. Our doctors mostly already have loyal patients and only practice in Assyifa Specialist Clinic for a clinic level. Therefore, our specialist doctors become our competitive advantages that should be put forward as the main character in communicating to the customers. The communication objectives to the proposed target market are to increase patient visits and customer acquisition, so that the customers will be triggered to visit the Assyifa Specialist Clinic by its doctors and effective marketing communication approach.

4.2.3 Create the Communications

Based on the author’s survey results, the most attractive content marketing are the information about treatment sales promotion/ discount, health education and reviews from patient/ family of patients. Besides, free health screening test, health seminar/ webinar and health talk-show are become the most attractive health events and sales promotion/ discount, giveaway or door prize of health products and free gift voucher treatment are the most attractive health promotion. Therefore, the author suggested that the brand message should be delivered from the specialist doctors through health seminar, webinars or talk-show to deliver health education that align with the service that provided from Assyifa facilities and treatment along with the patient journey and positive reviews in receiving the treatment from the Assyifa clinic. Then, several audiences will be drawn in winning the door prize of health products, free gift voucher treatment and certain treatment promotion/ discount and the event closed with free health screening test.

4.2.4 Choose the Communications Channels

According to the author’s survey results, most attractive advertising promotion are from Instagram social media such as feeds, story and reels, website and WhatsApp message. So, the communication channels should be formed and developed through two types of communication channels which are personal communication channels and mass communication channels as follows:

Table 3. Proposed Communication Channels

<i>Mass Communication Channels</i>	
Offline	Online
- Printed banner in potential areas (Assyifa’s front areas that close with traffic lights and roads)	Social media
- Printed brochure/ pamphlet to the Assyifa’s visitors	Website
- Printed clinic name cards	Video platform (Youtube, Tiktok)
- Health events (seminars, talkshow, training/ workshop)	Health event (webinars)
<i>Personal Communication Channels</i>	
Offline	Online
- Health screening test	WhatsApp message
	Chat box in website
	Direct message from social media
	Call center

4.2.5 Decide the Communications Mix

There are eight types of communications platforms which are advertising, sales promotion, events and experiences, public relations and publicity, online and social media marketing, mobile marketing, direct and database marketing, and personal selling. The proposed communication mix of Assyifa Specialist Clinic will be mentioned as below:

Table 4. Proposed Communication Mix

<i>Advertising</i>	<i>Sales promotion</i>
Assyifa can establish the advertising communication platform through printed banner, brochure/ pamphlet, name cards and other display signs such signpost in the roads to deliver the existence of Assyifa Specialist Clinic and the information regarding clinic’s type of service, facilities and doctor practice hours as well as the health events and sales promotions information.	Assyifa could develop the giveaway health products/ vitamin campaigns, free gift voucher, treatment discounts and packages for new customers/ patients who haven’t visited and received any medication and treatment from Assyifa Specialist Clinic, for those who follow, promote and subscribe Assyifa social media and frequently visited Assyifa Specialist Clinic in a year. Besides, Assyifa could also establish the treatment, consultation and screening test discount through the national or international health awareness days and campaigns that honor the celebration day of some certain illness.
<i>Events and experiences</i>	<i>Public relations and publicity</i>
Assyifa can organize the sports events such as fun bike for bikers community, fun walk for kids, aerobic for elderly, yoga, Zumba dance and pound fit for female patients/ participants especially housewife and prenatal yoga for pregnant women. Other than that, Assyifa can establish free health screening test and mass vaccination program as well to increase customer experience toward Assyifa service and brand image.	Assyifa can organize the seminars, webinars and talk show periodically that invites the patients, media relations, government bodies and healthcare communities such the networks from other hospitals, clinics and public health centres to strengthen the relation and expand the market.
<i>Online and social media marketing</i>	<i>Mobile marketing</i>
Assyifa can develop online platform marketing through website that provide formal information regarding Assyifa operational hours, type of service, facilities, doctor practice hours, health events, sales promotion and added with chat box or forum to increase the patient interaction. Besides, Assyifa could also develop Youtube and Tiktok video for younger segments to provide the content such as health education, healthy lifestyle and also Assyifa’s type of service, treatment and facilities information.	Assyifa can develop mobile marketing through WhatsApp message, social media such as Instagram and Tiktok to provide clinic information regarding type of service, operational and practice hours and facilities directly, health education and service promotion/ discount content marketing and customer service through direct message, so that customers can free to ask any confidentially questions regarding type of service according to their disease respectively.
<i>Direct and database marketing</i>	<i>Personal selling</i>
Assyifa can create a catalogue that consist of type of service, treatment provided, facilities and tariff of the treatment as well as the administration flow, so the patient would be familiar with the company’s knowledge and information they need to make the best treatment and service decisions.	Assyifa can develop sales meetings and presentations to other clinics and hospitals to build beneficial collaboration, new business line and increase treatment referrals as Assyifa has many competitive advantages in clinic level and has strong position in the market.

4.3 Value Proposition

According to the author’s survey results, the most values perceived by customers from Assyifa Specialist Clinic are they gain high quality of doctor service, easy to find and access of clinic’s strategic location, affordable treatment price and the fast service and administration quality. Meanwhile, for the least values that perceived by customers are clinic promotion and the access of clinic information. Hence, the value proposition canvas of Assyifa Specialist Clinic would be illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 1. Assyifa Specialist Clinic Value Proposition Canvas

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, after experiencing a financial downturn and the operational turbulence due to Covid-19 outbreak occurred, Assyifa Specialist Clinic gradually adjust its business activities to be able to operate in the midst of Covid-19 pandemic. Some of which by starting to conduct the face-to-face consultation and treatment of specialist doctors and dental practice by facilitating with a safe equipment and infrastructure. Moreover, the Covid-19 pandemic also affected to the internet and social media penetration which significantly increase the online communications platform users such as search engine/ website and social media. Besides, people nowadays tend to become more aware to their health issue and conditions as well. Therefore, this study aims to propose Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) and customer value proposition canvas to increase patient visits through providing the current relevant segmenting, targeting and positioning, so that the message can be appropriately delivered and the marketing initiative strategy can be organized properly to the customers who live around Jabodetabek (Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, Bekasi) area in the age between 26 – 55 years old both female/ male with the occupation are employee and housewife at middle to high income level, have health conscious, social media users, technology savvy, financially literate, well-educated and hygiene conscious lifestyle and critical, curious, high self-awareness, smart and generous personality who seek the healthcare value from its quality of service, pleasant experience, adequate facilities, positive review, affordable tariff of treatment, strategic location, easy to find, safe and hygienic environment. The IMC strategy would by establishing advertising (printed banner, brochure/ pamphlet, name cards), sales promotion (the giveaway health products/ vitamin campaigns, free gift voucher, treatment discounts and packages), events and experiences such sport events, public relations and publicity (seminar, webinar, talk show, health screening test and mass vaccination program), online and social media marketing (Website, Youtube, Tiktok), mobile marketing (WhatsApp and Instagram), direct and database marketing such catalogue and personal selling (sales meetings and presentations). Then, the customers value proposition canvas would be strengthened the high quality of doctor service, the access of clinic’s strategic location, affordable treatment price and the fast service and administration quality and improved the clinic promotion and the access of clinic information.

